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IC_SBFLRP3S_DMPLA_2022091856618_PLCMNT_EXPORT	230	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
IC_SBFLRP3S_DMPLA_2022091856618_PLCMNT_EXPORT	231	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
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IC_SBFLRP3S_DMPLA_2022091856618_PLCMNT_EXPORT	240	SBFLRP3S	09/18/2022	LOW027
IC_SBFLRP3S_DMPLA_2022091856618_PLCMNT_EXPORT	241	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
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IC_SBFLRP3S_DMPLA_2022091856618_PLCMNT_EXPORT	250	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]

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LanguageIndicator	BrwrFirstName	BrwrMiddlsName	BrwrLastName	BrwrSuffix	BrwrSSN	BrwrDOB
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CROSSREF4 CROSSREF5 CROSSREF6 CROSSREF7 CROSSREF8 CROSSREF9 CROSSREF10

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